

Environmental Management and Rural Planning: A Case Study of Banka District (Bihar)

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Abstract

Environment is very crucial for human development. Both physical and human environments influence the socio-economic development of any region. Geographically, Banka district forms a south-eastern part of the Anga plain situated in the Middle Ganga Valley. The district presents a dual picture of hilly as well as plain area. The district is primarily a backward and rural one facing major environmental challenges. Agriculture sector requires much more care, whereas waste and barren land requires specific treatment. The main purpose of the paper is to highlight environmental awareness and suggest strategy for suitable management and sustainable regional development in such a backward rural setting.

Keywords

Environment, Management, Sustainable, Rural, Barren etc

Introduction

Environment means everything around us, namely land, water, air, plants, animals, forests, minerals, and also human beings. The environment surrounding us has physical, social, and cultural dimensions. Deterioration in any of these affects the others, and in turn all jointly affect the environment. When environmental factors act against nature, it leads to various environmental disasters and hazards which make the life of organisms, including man, full of misery. Both physical and human environments influence the socio-economic development of any region. Environment exerts profound influence on man's habitat, economy, and society. All human traits, behaviour, and culture are conditioned by the physical environment. Man, being the most conscious and wisest of all living creatures on earth, exploits natural resources to satisfy his increasing wants without taking care of their destruction and resultant adverse impact on the ecosystem. Man's constant unconscious behaviour towards his physical surroundings finally leads to ecological disharmony and overall environmental degradation. Despite the fact that environmental awareness at various levels is being created for protection and conservation, resources are being harnessed indiscriminately. The uncontrolled growth of population and increased pressure on limited natural resources have contributed to ecological imbalance. The phenomenal growth of population and the increased resource consumption are major factors responsible for gradual environmental degradation.

Scarcity of arable lands, soil erosion, land degradation, irrational use of land, water shortage, and salinization have now become universal ecological problems. Biological diversity, which is very important for agriculture at many levels, is seriously threatened. The exploitation of agricultural land at the expense of forests and pastures and the subsequent adverse impact on wildlife have resulted in ecological imbalance. Continued destruction and pollution of environmental resources go unchecked, and if not checked in time, the very existence of human life and civilization will be at stake. Keeping in view the grave, challenging and burning issues like multi-pronged attack on environment, the paper aims to highlight the concept of awareness and management for sustainable rural development in a backward rural setting.

Objective of study

The purpose of the study is to provide an understanding about the man-environment interaction and its role towards making balance between man and ecological environments. The chief aims are to investigate various resources of the study area and to examine the levels of their use and misuse, to assess and analyse the relevance of environmental management for rural planning.

Review of Literature

The study of environment and its management is a new addition in the different disciplines. Baldwin J.H. (1988) has authored a book entitled 'Environmental Planning and Management.' Negi, P. (2001) has edited a book 'Environment, Population and Development.'

M.M. Pandey (2006) has written an article 'Management and Utilisation of Water Resources in Bihar.' Chopra, D.P. (1985) has written a book on 'Rural Development Planning in India.' The book by C.P. Singh (1985) 'Rural Development and Resources in a Developing Region' throws ample light in this direction. Bina Devi Singh (1992) has worked on Environmental Management : A Case Study of Sultanpur District Besides the above, a lot of work has been done in this field which constitutes the basis of the present study.

Main Text**Study Area**

Geographically, Banka district forms the south-eastern part of South Bihar plain. With an area of 3,020 sq. kms and a population of 16,08,733 persons (2011), the whole district is predominantly rural, with about 96% of the population living in villages. It has a compact shape comprising eleven C.D. Blocks. The district has only three urban centres. Most rural settlements have come up along main routes. The district is bounded in the south east and west by the districts of Deoghar, Dumka, and Godda of Jharkhand State.

Physiographically, the district is a combination of featureless plain in the north and undulating topography in the south. There is a large coverage of waste and barren land in the south. Agriculture forms the mainstay of the economy in the region. The district is inhabited by tribes, scheduled castes and backward caste people which constitute a considerable proportion of the population. The infrastructural facilities are poorly available to the dwellers. The socio-economic condition of the people is governed by environmental conditions. The large area covered by forests as well as wasteland requires better treatment and planning. The rural development is closely linked with proper and rational management of its resources, physical as well as human, in such a backward district of Bihar.

Physical and Human Environment

So far as the availability of physical resources is concerned, Banka district possesses land, water, forest as well as mineral resources. Land is adequately available but fertile land is limited. Barren and wastelands are in plenty. The forest cover is also limited. Water resources are available but utilization of water is not properly managed. Chandan, Chir, Barua, and Gerua are big rivers which carry water and sand. Minerals are found in limited quantity. There is much scope for the production of food crops by utilizing land, water, vegetation, and forest cover and management of physical environment. After detailed analysis of physical resources, the development of the region may be initiated and planning measures can be fully implemented.

Occupational Structure of Population of the district is not good. A large number of people are non-workers. They migrate to big cities of India in search of livelihood. The population of the district is also increasing rapidly. Literacy is also not up to the mark.

Land is one of the important components of the life-supporting system and is being overused or abused. At the present rate of population growth, land cannot meet the long-term demands of food, fuel, fodder, and shelter at reasonable costs. The arable land area is shrinking continuously because of unplanned urbanization, deforestation, unscientific and indiscriminate construction of housing estates, and use of agricultural land for industrial purposes.

Planning Measures

A meticulous planning is needed for implementation of agricultural practices in a proper manner. The need of the hour is to increase productivity of crops per unit area and per person of agricultural population with a green revolution technology. There is vast increase in sugarcane production besides paddy, wheat, and maize as well as coarse crops. A vast chunk of barren and wastelands available in Chanan and Katoria blocks may be made available by erecting embankments on rivers and rainwater storage in reservoirs, so that water stored can be used for irrigation purposes. Agriculture is the most important resource of the district, with 55% of land under cultivation. Integrated water resource management is the key for sustainable watershed development. Agro-based industries need promotion. Massive afforestation is required on a priority basis. Indigenous resources should be properly utilized to meet the basic needs of the majority of people. Population explosion is a vital challenge which must be tackled rationally. Educational awareness is the most important part which can help in population planning as well as control of depletion of natural resources.

Conclusion

Banka District is a transitional part of Bihar State which connects it with the State of Jharkhand. Banka District presents both hilly and plain areas. The land, water, and forest etc have not been utilised in an optimum way. Therefore, it is required that agriculture should be modernised, water resources should be conserved, forest resources should be developed, industrial development especially small and medium scale should be promoted on an indigenous basis, the infrastructural development should be geared up through environmental consciousness for its proper utilisation and conservation, the region can find real uplift, and only then the all-round prosperity can be ensured.

References

1. Chandpuri (2004) : *Regional Planning in India*, Rawat Publication, Daryaganj, New Delhi.
2. Chattopadhyay, B.C. (1985) : *Rural Development Planning in India*, S. Chand & Company Ltd., New Delhi.
3. Nag, P. et al. (2001) : *Environment, Population and Development*, Concept Publication, New Delhi.
4. Rana, U.P. (2000) : *Changing Pattern of Agricultural Land in the District of Banka, Bihar, Geographical Perspective, Vol. I, pp. 47-51.*
5. Singh, Ram Pyare (2001): *Bihar: Resource and Planning*, Janaki Prakashan, Patna.
6. Sharma, B.R. (1987): *Environmental Management in India : An Overview*, in R.K. Sapru (ed.), Vol. II, Ashish Publishing Co., New Delhi.